

Ptolemaic Egypt - Egyptian Religion

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This entry consists of data that refers to what we today call Egyptian religion, dating to the "Ptolemaic Period". It is a stage of the Egyptian cults that immediately followed the previous epochs and used the conventional Egyptian motifs, practices and texts in its forms of expression. Egyptian religion was not ethnically bound, but exerted a great attraction also on the immigrants in Egypt. In principle, it was open to everyone to participate in the local cults.

Date Range: 304 BCE - 30 BCE

Region: Ancient Egypt - Ptolemaic Period

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Egypt

Egypt during the Ptolemaic Period

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Dunand, F./Zivie-Coche, Chr., Gods and men in Egypt : 3000 BCE to 395 CE. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2004
- Source 2: Sauneron, S., The priests of ancient Egypt. New York: Grove Press, 1980
- Source 3: Zivie-Coche, Chr./Dunand, F., Die Religionen des Alten Ägypten. Stuttgart: W. Kohlhammer, 2013

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://escholarship.org/uc/nelc_uee
- Source 2 URL: <https://oeb.griffith.ox.ac.uk/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.egyptologyforum.org/EEFtexts.html>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the Egyptian majority population (approx. 95%), numerous immigrants lived in Egypt in Hellenistic times, primarily Greeks and Macedonians, but also other people from the regions of the northeastern Mediterranean with their respective religions. In particular, a large minority group consisted of Jewish individuals. Egyptian religion itself was highly resilient to foreign influences.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 7000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 95

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: There were numerous hymns, prayers, ritual representations, staged myths, which on the one hand are written down in Egyptian temple representations and partly also illustrated. On the other hand, there is also a rich tradition of religious literature handed down in demotic script on papyrus. Altogether one can speak of a temporal continuum: The religion of Egypt has evolved over time, but fundamentally it does not differ significantly from what we have already come to know in previous periods. However, many thoughts that existed centuries before are described in more detail in

Hellenistic times, many myths we get to know in their concrete contents only during the Ptolemaic period.

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
– I don't know

– I don't know

Notes: The temples of Ancient Egypt can be small shrines up to complex sacred precincts comprising many temples (Karank e.g. covers 30 hektar).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:
– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
 - Yes
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

- ↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...
 - Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: In the Ptolemaic Period, the dead could live on in three main spheres. That would be firstly the earth, secondly the sky, in which the dead wants to be with the sun god Re, and thirdly the underworld, in which Osiris rules and into which the dead enters after passing the so-called judgement of the dead. The tomb, in turn, is the decisive place of contact with this world, the body is ultimately placed there, and the tomb allows the dead to participate in life. The action of "coming forth by day," as the literature on the dead (popularly referred to as the Book of the Dead) puts it, formed the epitome of afterlife desires from the New Kingdom on.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– I don't know

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: This is a very difficult question, because each Egyptian nome had a central god, whom I would like to call therefore in each case high-god. Of special, almost pan-Egyptian importance were Osiris, Isis and Horus, but especially in Thebes Amun-Ra and in Memphis Ptah. I consider them as high-gods because they took a central position in the very different creation myths. In most cases the high-gods did not stand alone, but formed a triad of gods with a wife and a child. However, I must admit at the same time that first it would have to be clarified theologically perfectly what a high-god is, what are his qualities. Depending on the definition

then also exclusively Amun-Re could be called such.

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s)

within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - I don't know

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No

 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No

 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: oracles
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - No
 - ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The experience of foreign domination led to a prophetic literature that resulted in hopes for a new messiah-king who would liberate Egypt from the calamity (of foreign domination). Relevant to this is the oracle of the potter. Messianic belief can also be found in New Kingdom texts.

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - No
- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes
- ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The social norms are summarized in the so-called negative confessions - book of the dead spell No. 124. They are based on the principle of the Golden Rule and the principle of protecting and supporting the poor, widows and orphans.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Usually, Egyptian priests performed cult actions in the temple (which was inaccessible to lay people) to the exclusion of the public. Only during large festive processions was it possible for the population to come into contact with the deity – each nome had its own festivals. For this purpose, the deity “visited” another temple and there were feasts and consumption of alcohol by the population. The deity could also be approached as an oracle during such processions.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: During the Ptolemaic period, the Egyptians had a differentiated legal system with their own courts of so-called laokritai, which operated alongside the Greek courts. There is also a legal code, the so-called codex of Hermopolis.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No